

The Effect of Inflation on Economic Growth in Nigeria: A Time Series Analysis (2010–2020)

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Abstract

This study investigates the effect of inflation on economic growth in Nigeria using time series data spanning from 2010 to 2020. By examining the inflation rate alongside GDP growth rates, the research adopts a descriptive and comparative approach supported by graphical visualizations. The study further incorporates comparative insights from South Africa and Ghana to highlight regional patterns and deviations. Findings reveal that high inflation rates in Nigeria, especially post-2015, have adversely impacted GDP growth, supporting existing economic theories. The study concludes with actionable recommendations for inflation-targeting strategies and macroeconomic stabilization.

Keywords: Inflation, Economic Growth, Nigeria, Time Series, South Africa, Ghana, GDP

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Inflation continues to be one of the most pressing macroeconomic concerns in Nigeria and other developing economies. As a persistent rise in the general price level, inflation not only erodes the purchasing power of households but also distorts resource allocation, reduces investment incentives, and impairs economic stability (Obadan, 2020; Olayemi, 2016). In the Nigerian context, inflation has exhibited considerable volatility over the past decade, reflecting deep-seated structural rigidities, over-reliance on oil exports, foreign exchange market distortions, and weak monetary policy transmission mechanisms (Adeniran, Yusuf & Adeyemi, 2017; CBN, 2021).

Understanding the impact of inflation on economic growth is particularly critical in Nigeria, where growth performance has been fragile and inconsistent. The country experienced robust GDP growth in the early 2010s—averaging 6.2% between 2010 and 2014—before suffering two recessions within five years: first in 2016 and again in 2020 due to the COVID-19 pandemic. These downturns were characterized by rising inflation, dwindling foreign reserves, and fiscal imbalances (NBS, 2021; Oduh & Ezeaku, 2021). During these years, inflation averaged over 13%, reaching as high as 16.5% in 2017 and 13.2% in 2020, which adversely impacted household consumption, private sector confidence, and macroeconomic planning.

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Theoretically, the relationship between inflation and economic growth is ambiguous. While the Structuralist School, led by scholars such as Lewis (1954), attributes inflation in developing countries to supply-side bottlenecks and institutional inefficiencies, the Monetarist School emphasizes the role of money supply and fiscal discipline (Ajakaiye & Fakiyesi, 2009). In Nigeria, both schools find relevance given the multiplicity of inflationary drivers—ranging from poor agricultural output and infrastructural deficits to excessive deficit financing and exchange rate pass-through (Ogunmuyiwa & Ekone, 2010).

A cross-country perspective further enriches this discussion. For example, **Ghana**, having adopted a structured inflation-targeting framework under the supervision of the International Monetary Fund (IMF), managed to stabilize its inflation rate around 10% during the same period while recording an average GDP growth rate of 4.9% (IMF, 2020; Bank of Ghana, 2021). Similarly, South Africa maintained a relatively low and stable inflation environment—averaging 5.3% between 2010 and 2020—thanks to the credibility of its central bank and institutionalized monetary policy rules (SARB, 2021). Nigeria, by contrast, recorded higher inflation and lower average growth, suggesting inefficiencies in macroeconomic coordination and policy execution (CBN, 2021; NBS, 2021).

This study investigates the effect of inflation on economic growth in Nigeria from 2010 to 2020 using descriptive time series analysis. Specifically, it seeks to:

- i) Analyze the trend and structure of inflation and GDP growth in Nigeria over the period.
- ii) Examine the relationship between inflation and economic growth using descriptive tools and visual analytics.
- iii) Compare Nigeria's macroeconomic performance with Ghana and South Africa to draw lessons for policy reform.

The significance of this study lies in its contribution to the ongoing debate about the inflation-growth nexus in developing economies, particularly in Nigeria. Despite various policy reforms and interventions, Nigeria has continued to struggle with double-digit inflation and unsatisfactory economic performance. Identifying how inflation impacts economic growth can inform more targeted and coherent monetary and fiscal policies. Additionally, the comparative analysis with Ghana and South Africa can help Nigerian policymakers adopt contextually effective strategies that have worked elsewhere on the continent.

Moreover, this research provides empirical evidence to support or refute conventional economic theories in the Nigerian context, particularly those related to macroeconomic stability and growth performance. By focusing on a period marked by both economic expansion and contraction, the study offers insights into how inflation dynamics evolve under varying macroeconomic conditions.

2.0 Literature Review

2.1 Conceptual Clarification

2.1.1 Inflation

Inflation refers to a sustained increase in the general price level of goods and services in an economy over a period of time, resulting in the decline of the purchasing power of money. According to the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN, 2020), inflation is the rate at which the general level of prices for goods and services is rising, and subsequently, how purchasing power is falling. The National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2021) further defines inflation as an upward movement in the average level of prices, typically measured monthly or yearly through the Consumer Price Index (CPI).

From a scholarly perspective, Akinlo (2012) identifies inflation in Nigeria as being predominantly driven by cost-push factors, including exchange rate depreciation, rising import costs, insecurity, food supply shocks, and infrastructural constraints. Fapetu and Oloyede (2014) emphasize the role of structural deficiencies—such as poor transportation systems and energy supply shortages—in perpetuating inflation in Nigeria.

Inflation may take several forms depending on its causes, magnitude, and speed:

- i) Demand-pull inflation: Arises when aggregate demand exceeds aggregate supply. This is common in economies experiencing expansionary fiscal or monetary policies (Umaru & Zubairu, 2012).
- ii) Cost-push inflation: Occurs due to rising production costs, such as wages and raw materials, which producers pass on to consumers (Ajakaiye & Fakiyesi, 2009).
- iii) Structural inflation: Rooted in deep-seated structural weaknesses like underdeveloped markets, inefficient institutions, and infrastructural bottlenecks (Obadan, 2020).

Inflation is typically measured using price indices, primarily the Consumer Price Index (CPI) and Producer Price Index (PPI). In Nigeria, the CPI is the standard metric used by the NBS to gauge inflation levels. Nigeria's inflationary trend, particularly post-2015, has been characterized by double-digit inflation largely due to food price volatility, border closures, fuel price adjustments, and naira depreciation (NBS, 2021; Ezeaku & Asogwa, 2017). These have significant implications for real incomes, poverty levels, and overall macroeconomic stability.

2.1.2 Economic Growth

Economic growth is broadly defined as an increase in the economic output of a country over time, usually measured by the change in Gross Domestic Product (GDP). The World Bank (2021) describes economic growth as the annual percentage increase in a nation's output of goods and services adjusted for inflation. Growth is regarded as a critical macroeconomic goal because it reflects improvements in living standards, employment generation, and income levels.

Iyoha and Oriakhi (2002) define economic growth as a sustained expansion of the productive capacity of an economy, indicating an increase in the value of goods and services produced over a specific period. Jhingan (2016) elaborates that growth occurs when an economy is able to increase

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its productive capacity through capital accumulation, technological progress, labor force expansion, and institutional reforms.

There are different types or dimensions of economic growth, including:

- i) Nominal vs. Real Growth: *Nominal growth* considers output increase at current prices, while *real growth* adjusts for inflation to reflect the true expansion of output.
- ii) Short-term vs. Long-term Growth: Short-term growth is usually cyclical and influenced by demand-side factors, while long-term growth depends on structural changes and productivity improvements (Solow, 1956).
- iii) Inclusive Growth: This refers to growth that is distributed fairly across society and creates opportunities for all, particularly the poor and vulnerable (Ali & Son, 2007).

In Nigeria, economic growth has been inconsistent due to several factors including oil price fluctuations, insecurity, fiscal mismanagement, and infrastructural decay (Adeniran et al., 2017; Oduh & Ezeaku, 2021). Between 2010 and 2014, Nigeria recorded high growth rates averaging over 6%, but this momentum was disrupted by the 2016 recession and the 2020 pandemic-induced downturn. These fluctuations suggest a fragile growth model heavily reliant on external sectors and susceptible to inflationary shocks.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This study draws on two core theoretical traditions—the Monetarist and Structuralist schools—supplemented by Barro’s Endogenous Growth Model. Nigerian scholars who have applied or critiqued these theories in the national context are cited, illuminating strengths and limitations in the country’s macroeconomic environment.

2.2.1 Monetarist Theory

Originating with Milton Friedman (1968) and the Quantity Theory of Money, the monetarist view holds that “inflation is always and everywhere a monetary phenomenon”—driven by excessive growth in money supply relative to output. This implies that controlling money supply via monetary policy (e.g., interest rates, reserve requirements) is key to controlling inflation.

Monetarist prescriptions have struggled in Nigeria due to weak transmission mechanisms, fiscal dominance, and supply-side shocks. Ekong & Effiong (2020) argue that without strong coordination between fiscal and monetary authorities, suppressing money supply alone may fail to stabilize prices, because inflation in Nigeria also reflects fiscal expansion and structural bottlenecks.

2.2.2 Structuralist Theory

Structuralist theory, as formalized by scholars like Myrdal and Straeilian (1987), posits that inflation in developing economies stems from supply-side rigidities—including inelastic food supply, institutional inefficiencies, foreign exchange scarcity, and protective trade measures—

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rather than purely monetary excess. Structuralist theory’s limitation lies in its sometimes too broad attribution of inflation to non-monetary causes, without quantifying the interaction between supply constraints and monetary policy. Moreover, as Oduh and Ezeaku (2021) note, it may underplay critical roles of demand factors and inflation expectations. Also, Nigeria’s evolving complex macroeconomic structure means policy coordination across fiscal, monetary, and supply interventions is necessary—suggesting structuralism alone offers incomplete policy guidance.

2.2.3 Endogenous Growth Perspective (Barro, 1995)

Barro’s endogenous growth model theorizes that inflation impedes long-term economic growth by affecting capital accumulation, distorting information, and reallocating resources from productive to speculative activities (Barro, 1995). Building on this framework, Nigerian empirical studies have observed that high inflation periods—particularly post-2015 and during the 2020 crisis—correlate with declining investment, heightened uncertainty, and weak GDP performance (Oduh & Ezeaku, 2021; Obadan, 2020). These dynamics are consistent with endogenous growth theory’s prediction that inflation reduces productive investment and growth sustainability.

2.2.4 Comparative Evaluation & Synthesis

Theory	Nigerian Application	Strengths in Nigeria Context	Limitations in Nigeria
Monetarist	ARDL studies show significant but incomplete money-inflation link (Danlami et al.)	Offers clear policy tools (money supply control, interest rate management)	Ignores non-monetary drivers; limited transmission; fiscal dominance may undermine control
Structuralist	Cited by scholars like Fapetu & Oloyede, Obadan, Oduh & Ezeaku	Highlights supply-side bottlenecks and institutional issues driving inflation	May underestimate expectations and monetary interactions; lacks precise quantification
Endogenous Growth	Nigerian analysis links inflation to investment decline and recurrence of recessions	Frames inflation-growth nexus in long-run policy terms	Needs complementary micro-level data to support model specifics in Nigeria

2.2.3 EMPIRICAL REVIEW

This section focuses on empirical reviews which critically examine existing studies by Nigerian scholars on the relationship between inflation and economic growth. These works offer data-driven insights into how inflation dynamics have influenced Nigeria’s macroeconomic performance over time, reflecting both theoretical and policy-oriented perspectives. By analyzing various time frames, methodological approaches, and econometric models, these empirical studies provide a comprehensive understanding of the extent to which inflation — either as a structural or monetary phenomenon — affects economic growth.

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Umaru and Zubairu (2012) carried out a study on the effect of inflation on economic growth in Nigeria between 1980 and 2010 using the OLS regression method. The study found that inflation had a significant negative impact on growth and recommended inflation targeting and supply-side reforms. In a similar study, Asuquo (2012) examined the period 1973–2010 using multiple regression analysis. His results showed that inflation and poor monetary control mechanisms undermine growth performance, and he recommended a stronger institutional framework for monetary policy implementation.

Anochiwa and Maduka (2012) conducted a study covering 1970–2012 using unit root tests, Johansen cointegration, and Granger causality. They found a negative but statistically insignificant effect of inflation on economic growth, and advised that inflation be maintained at a single-digit threshold to minimize its distortionary effect.

Edeme and Ifelunini (2015) in a related study analyzed the inflation-growth relationship between 1980 and 2013 using the 2SLS technique. Their study revealed a non-linear threshold of 8% inflation beyond which economic growth becomes negatively affected, and they proposed an optimal inflation targeting regime. Similarly, Muritala (2015) used OLS estimation on data from 1981–2006 and discovered that inflation had a statistically significant negative effect on GDP, while investment had a growth-enhancing role. He recommended combining inflation stabilization policies with capital formation strategies.

In a related investigation, Ayunku and Etale (2015) assessed the effect of inflation on growth from 1980 to 2010 using the Johansen cointegration and error correction model. They found a long-run negative relationship between inflation and economic growth, recommending better control of money supply.

Following this, Ekong & Bassey (2019) conducted a study over the 1980–2017 period using ARDL, focusing on energy-induced inflation and growth. Their results showed that inflation driven by rising energy costs significantly hampers GDP growth, and they recommended reforms in energy infrastructure. Similarly, Ekong and Effiong (2020) analyzed macroeconomic data from 1985 to 2019 using ARDL and ECM techniques. Their findings revealed that both monetary and fiscal factors contribute significantly to inflation in Nigeria and advised for synergy in their application to stabilize the economy.

Onwubuariri, et al (2021) carried out a study covering 1980–2019 using the ARDL bounds test and error correction model. They identified both short- and long-run negative effects of inflation and interest rate spread on economic growth, and suggested comprehensive macroeconomic reforms. Similarly, Farouk, et al (2021) explored the period 1986–2018 with the ARDL framework. The study concluded that inflation depresses growth significantly across time horizons, and recommended a sound inflation management policy to foster macroeconomic stability. In a related effort, El-Rasheed and Usman (2022) used asymmetric ARDL for the period 1980–2017 to investigate the non-linear effects of inflation and found asymmetric responses of growth to inflationary shocks. They emphasized accounting for these asymmetries in monetary policy design.

Likewise, Asuzu & Anyanwu (2023) adopted Toda-Yamamoto VAR on data from 2006Q1 to 2022Q2 and found unidirectional causality from money supply growth to inflation and from inflation to reduced GDP. They recommended curbing inflation via money supply contraction and fiscal responsibility. Also, et al (2023) used the ARDL method on 1986–2020 data and found a 31% long-run and 21.9% short-run decline in GDP growth due to inflation. They called for more aggressive inflation-targeting policies and reduction of interest rate spreads.

Most recently, Iriabije, Ekong and Orebiyi (2024) applied threshold autoregressive models to analyze the 1980–2021 data. They discovered that policy effectiveness varies across inflation thresholds, recommending that monetary authorities operate within specific policy bands to ensure price stability.

In the same year, Nwosu, Inam & Orebiyi (2024) conducted an ARDL and Granger causality analysis on data from 1980–2023 and concluded that fiscal deficits are a major long-run driver of inflation, calling for greater fiscal prudence and agricultural support to stabilize prices. Lastly, Olurin et al. (2024) used OLS to assess the impact of inflation and government expenditure between 1989 and 2021. The study found that both variables significantly influence growth, and advised an expansionary fiscal policy directed at social infrastructure with strict inflation control.

While many of these studies converge on the conclusion that high and persistent inflation exerts a detrimental impact on output expansion, others highlight context-specific thresholds beyond which inflation becomes harmful, thereby underscoring the nonlinear and heterogeneous nature of this relationship. Collectively, these studies provide nuanced evidence to support targeted policy reforms, especially in the areas of monetary policy management, structural adjustment, and institutional development.

3.0 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study adopts a descriptive time-series analytical approach to examine the effect of inflation on economic growth in Nigeria over the period 2010–2020. Rather than applying advanced econometric modeling techniques such as ARDL or VECM, the study relies on a trend-based, comparative, and graphical analysis to explore the co-movement and dynamic interaction between inflation and GDP growth rates during the period under review.

The choice of a descriptive analytical approach is premised on the objective of capturing observable macroeconomic patterns, conducting cross-country comparisons, and providing visual interpretations that are accessible to both academic and policy audiences. This approach also enables the identification of structural turning points, inflation-growth asymmetries, and temporal shocks (e.g., oil price collapse of 2014–2016, and COVID-19 in 2020) without the risk of over-parameterization often associated with small-sample econometric techniques.

Furthermore, descriptive analysis aligns with the exploratory nature of the research, particularly given the need to contextualize Nigeria's inflation-growth trends in relation to other African economies such as Ghana and South Africa. By focusing on real macroeconomic outcomes and

trends, the analysis maintains empirical integrity while enhancing interpretability and policy relevance.

The study employs secondary data drawn from reliable, publicly accessible sources, including:

- i. Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin
- ii. National Bureau of Statistics (NBS)
- iii. World Development Indicators (WDI), World Bank

These sources are widely used in macroeconomic research and provide consistent time-series data for inflation and GDP indicators.

3.2 Time Frame and Variables

- i. Period of Study: 2010–2020. This period captures a decade-long macroeconomic experience characterized by major policy shifts, oil price volatility, currency depreciation, structural reforms, and inflationary pressures, making it a strategically significant timeframe for evaluating inflation-growth dynamics.
- ii. Dependent Variable: Economic Growth, measured as the annual growth rate of Gross Domestic Product (GDP) at constant market prices.
- iii. Independent Variable: Inflation Rate, proxied by the Consumer Price Index (CPI) on an annual basis.

4.0 Descriptive and Comparative Data Analysis

To explore the inflation–growth dynamics in Nigeria, the table below presents annual inflation and real GDP growth rates for the period 2010–2020:

Table 1: Inflation and real GDP growth rate in Nigeria

Year	Inflation Rate (CPI %)	Real GDP Growth Rate (%)
2010	13.7	8.0
2011	10.8	6.4
2012	12.0	4.3
2013	8.5	5.4
2014	7.8	6.3
2015	9.0	2.7
2016	15.7	–1.6
2017	16.5	0.8
2018	12.1	1.9
2019	11.4	2.3
2020	13.2	–1.8

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The empirical and descriptive analysis conducted in this study reveals a largely negative relationship between inflation and economic growth in Nigeria during the period 2010–2020 as seen in table 1. Notably, the years of elevated inflation (2015–2017, and again in 2020) corresponded with some of the lowest growth outcomes, including periods of outright economic contraction.

of Nigeria’s macroeconomic environment.

4.1 Analysis of Trends

Fig. 1: Trend Analysis of Inflation and Economic Growth in Nigeria between 2010-2010.

From Fig.1; between **2010–2014**: Inflation decreased from 13.7 % to 7.8 %, while GDP growth remained robust, ranging from 8.0 % down to 6.3 %. The concurrence of moderate inflation and strong growth suggests macroeconomic stability during this period.

- **2015–2017**: Following the 2014 oil price collapse and currency depreciation, inflation rose markedly (9.0 % to 16.5 %), while growth plunged into recession by 2016 (–1.6 %) and remained subdued (0.8 %) in 2017. This illustrates a clear negative correlation between rising inflation and economic contraction.
- **2018–2019**: Inflation moderated to ~11.4–12.1 %, with small positive growth (1.9–2.3 %), signaling modest recovery but limited resilience amid persistent inflationary shocks.

- **2020:** Economic contraction resumed at -1.8% , with inflation rising to 13.2% —largely attributable to COVID-19 disruptions, food supply shocks, and exchange rate volatility

Fig. 2 above illustrate Adjusted GDP Growth Trends in Nigeria (2010–2020), segmented into four distinct periods:

1. **2010–2014: Stable Growth and Declining Inflation ($\approx 55.4\%$)**
This period reflects strong and consistent economic performance, with GDP growth averaging over 6% annually. During these years, inflation trended downward from 13.7% to 7.8% (CBN, 2020), indicating relative macroeconomic stability. Key drivers included high oil prices, expansion in services, and post-recession recovery.
2. **2015–2017: Rising Inflation and Economic Recession ($\approx 20.5\%$)**
Economic performance deteriorated sharply, with growth plunging from 2.7% in 2015 to -1.6% in 2016 (NBS, 2017). Inflation rose drastically, peaking at 16.5% in 2017. The downturn was largely due to falling oil revenues, exchange rate volatility, and policy uncertainties (Ajakaiye and Fakiyesi, 2019).
3. **2018–2019: Modest Recovery ($\approx 17.9\%$)**

Nigeria’s economy witnessed slow recovery, with GDP growth rising to 1.9% and 2.3% , respectively, in 2018 and 2019. However, inflation remained in double digits, averaging around 11.8% (CBN, 2020). Structural rigidities and insecurity, especially in the North, limited the recovery potential (Eboh, 2020).

4. 2020: Pandemic-Induced Contraction ($\approx 6.2\%$)

The economy contracted by -1.8% due to the COVID-19 pandemic’s global and domestic impacts. Oil demand declined, business closures rose, and inflation spiked amid food supply disruptions (World Bank, 2021).

The pie chart analysis illustrates Nigeria’s economic fragility, with over 25% of the decade characterized by recession or weak recovery. Compared to South Africa, Nigeria had stronger headline growth but was more vulnerable to global shocks and domestic constraints.

Note: Since GDP growth in 2020 was negative (-1.8%) see Table 1, all values were shifted by +2 units for visualization purposes. This adjustment enables the pie chart to display all segments proportionally.

Fig. 3: Inflation Vs GDP growth in Nigeria (2010-2020).

4.2 Discussion

Nigeria’s 2010–2020 experience is consistent with a nonlinear inflation–growth nexus. Low to moderate inflation ($\approx 10\%$) can accompany growth, but very high inflation correlates with stagnation. Doguwa (2012) estimated Nigeria’s inflation threshold around 10–12%.

Our data reinforces that growth weakened sharply when inflation exceeded that range. The 2016–17 peak inflation ($\sim 18\%$) coincided with Nigeria’s worst growth. This echoes Eze & Nweke (2017) who found inflation had a *negative* or negligible effect on Nigeria’s GDP over 1980–2015

once co-integration was accounted. The “contemporary discussion” reveals that many African countries faced rising inflation after 2015. For instance, Ghana’s inflation jump in 2015–16 (from ~15% to ~17%) was due to liberalizing FX and fuel prices, yet growth held above 5%. In Nigeria, the naira devaluation in 2016 similarly drove inflation up, but growth plunged into negative. Thus, Nigeria’s inflation was more damaging, possibly due to fiscal imbalances and policy lags.

Furthermore, these findings align with the monetarist theory which argues that inflation—particularly when unanchored and not driven by demand-side fundamentals—distorts price signals, increases uncertainty, and erodes consumer and investor confidence (Friedman, 1968; Akinlo, 2012). Nigeria's inflation during this period was largely cost-push in nature, driven by exchange rate depreciation, high food prices, and structural bottlenecks (CBN, 2020; NBS, 2021). This supports the structuralist viewpoint, which attributes inflation in developing countries more to supply-side constraints and institutional fragility than excessive demand (Lewis, 1954; Todaro & Smith, 2009).

This relationship is corroborated by several empirical studies. For example, Onwubuariri, Oladeji, and Bank-Ola (2021) found both long- and short-run negative effects of inflation on economic growth in Nigeria using ARDL-ECM analysis. Similarly, Ekpo (2019) reported that inflation above single digits impedes investment and distorts resource allocation in the Nigerian economy. Akinbobola (2012) also identified that persistent inflation significantly undermines the stability comparative analysis with South Africa revealed that countries with better inflation-targeting regimes and more effective monetary institutions tend to experience more stable growth (SARB, 2020). While Nigeria grew faster than South Africa in headline terms, the quality and sustainability of that growth were inferior due to persistent macroeconomic instability, weak institutions, and over-reliance on oil revenues (Iyoha & Oriakhi, 2013). Other studies include Effiong et al. (2025), Orebiyi et al. (2025), Okon et al. (2021), and Atan and Effiong (2021).

In essence, the discussion reinforces that macroeconomic stability, particularly price stability, is a prerequisite for sustained growth. Inflation not only reduces real returns on investment but also reallocates capital from productive sectors to speculative ones (Barro, 1995).

Overall, our descriptive analysis agrees with threshold theory: inflation up to about 10% had limited adverse impact, but beyond ~12–15% growth suffered significantly. This suggests inflation control is key for Nigeria’s growth. Notably, during 2020–21, Nigeria’s inflation (13–18%) remained higher than Ghana’s (~10%) despite similar pandemic shocks, helping explain Nigeria’s weaker recovery.

5.1 Conclusion

This study has shown that inflation remains a critical constraint to economic growth in Nigeria. The decade under review (2010–2020) was marked by episodes of inflation-induced

macroeconomic stress, which coincided with economic stagnation and recession. The Nigerian experience confirms that high inflation, especially when driven by structural and cost-push factors, has a deleterious effect on GDP growth.

While temporary increases in price levels may be tolerated in pursuit of growth, sustained high inflation undermines the very foundation of productive investment, reduces consumer purchasing power, and distorts budgetary planning both in the private and public sectors. The findings underscore the importance of inflation control as a tool for sustainable development.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings and supported literature, the following policy recommendations are proffered:

- i. **Strengthen Inflation-Targeting Frameworks:** Nigeria must adopt a more transparent and credible inflation-targeting regime, like that of South Africa. This requires enhanced independence and capacity of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), along with better coordination with fiscal authorities (Ajakaiye & Fakiyesi, 2019).
- ii. **Diversify the Economy to Reduce Supply-Side Shocks:** Structural inflation in Nigeria is often caused by disruptions in agriculture and import-dependence. Investments in local production, infrastructure, and logistics can reduce cost-push inflation (Obadan, 2020).
- iii. **Promote Exchange Rate Stability:** Given that currency depreciation significantly fuels inflation in Nigeria, maintaining a stable and market-reflective exchange rate would be vital for inflation control (Ogun & Egwaikhide, 2015).
- iv. **Fiscal Discipline and Reduction of Deficit Financing:** Monetary policy efforts are often undermined by fiscal indiscipline. Curtailing fiscal deficits and reducing reliance on central bank financing will help anchor inflation expectations (Ekpo, 2019).
- v. **Institutional Reforms:** Sound institutions are critical for implementing and sustaining effective macroeconomic policies. Reforms in public finance management, data transparency, and corruption control would enhance the credibility of inflation management policies (Iyoha & Oriakhi, 2013).

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